

Understanding the Essence of the Indian Constitution Preamble.

Dr. Sudhir Kumar

Ph.D Political Science, L.N.Mithila University, Darbhanga

Corresponding Author – Dr. Sudhir Kumar

Email: Sudhirbrajesh@gmail.com

Abstract :

India's Constitution is the supreme law of India. It defines the Government's fundamental political values, policies, processes, powers, rights and duties. The Republic is governed in terms of the constitution of India which was adopted by the constituent Assembly on 26th November 1949 and came into force on 26th January 1950. The constitution provides for a Parliamentary form of government which is federal in structure with certain unitary features.

Keywords : Preamble, Constitution, Objectives, Equality, Justice, Liberty, Fraternity, Socialist, Secular, etc.

Introduction :

The preamble of the Indian constitution serves as the guiding light, encapsulating the ideals and aspirations that form the bedrock of the nation. Comprising a concise yet profound statement. It lays the foundation for the governance and principals that define the world's largest democracy. The preamble to the constitution of India presents the principals of the constitution and indicates the sources of its authority. It was adopted on 26 November 1949 by the constituent assembly and came into force on 26th November 1950, celebrated as the Republic Day of India. It was amended during the Indian emergency of Indira Gandhi where the words "Socialist", "Secular" and integrity" were added.

The Words of The Preamble

We, The People of India having solemnly resolved to constitute India into a [Sovereign Socialist Secular Democratic Republic] and to secure to all its citizens :

Justice, Social, economic and political; Liberty of thought, expression, belief, faith and worship; Equality of status and of opportunity, and to promote among them all.

Fraternity assuring the dignity of the individual and the unity and integrity of the nation. In Our Constituent Assembly this Twenty-sixth day of November 1949 do hereby Adopt, Enact and Give to Ourselves This Constitution.

What is a Preamble ?

A preamble is an introductory statement in a document that explain the document's philosophy and objectives.

In a constitution, it presents the intentions of its farmers, the history behind its creation, and the core values and principles of the nation.

The preamble basically gives idea of the following things/objects :

- Source of the Constitution
- Nature of Indian State
- Statement of Its objectives
- Date of its adoption.

Historical contract of the preamble to the Indian constitution :

As we know the preamble to the constitution of India was adopted on January 26, 1950 coinciding with the country's transition to a republic. It reflects the ideals and aspirations of the farmers of the constitution, who sought to establish a democratic and sovereign nation. The historical context includes India's struggle for independence from British rule, the drafting of the constitution by the constituent Assembly, and the commitment to justice, liberty, equality, and fraternity as outlined in the preamble. It serve as a guiding document, outlining the values and goals of the Indian state.

The ideals behind the preamble to India's constitution were laid down by Jawaharlal Nehru's objective resolution, adopted by the constituent assembly on January 22, 1947.

Although not enforceable in court, the preamble states the objectives of the constitution an acts as an aid during the interpretation of Articles when language is found unclear.

Component of Preamble :

1. It is indicated by the preamble that the source of authority of the constitution lies with the people of India.
2. Preamble declares India to be a sovereign, socialist, secular and democratic republic.
3. The objectives stated by the preamble are to source justice, liberty, equality to all citizens and promote fraternity to maintain unity and integrity of the nation.
4. The dates is mentioned in the preamble when it was adopted i.e. November 26, 1949.

Key Words in the Preamble

Secular and Democratic :

"Secular" and "Democratic" are pillars that upholds the fabric of Indian society. Secularism ensures religious harmony, while democracy empowers citizens through representation and participation. The interplay of these principles reflects the delicate balance required in a diverse and pluralistic nation.

Republic and Justice :

The concept of a "Republic" signifies a nation where power resides in the hands of the people. "Justice" forms the crux of the preamble, encompassing social, economic, and political justice. Unraveling these elements unravels the commitment to fairness, equity, and the rule of law.

Liberty and Equality :

"Liberty" and "Equality" echo the values cherished in a democratic society. They explore the delicate equilibrium between individual freedom and societal cohesion, providing insight into the constitutional framework designed to protect fundamental rights.

Fraternity :

The preamble concludes with the invocation of "Fraternity" highlighting the importance of brotherhood and unity. This serves as a poignant reminder of the diverse tapestry that is India and the imperative of fostering a sense of community amidst diversity.

Evolution of the Preamble :

Over the years, the preamble has witnessed subtle changes, reflecting the evolving aspirations of the nation. Legal interpretations and judicial pronouncements have further clarified its significance, solidifying its status as the soul of the constitution.

Challenges and Relevance :

In the contemporary landscape, the preamble faces challenges that test its resilience. From socio-economic disparities to cultural diversity, the preamble's enduring relevance lies in its ability to adopt and guide the nation through complex socio-political scenarios.

Objective of the Indian Preamble :

The objective of the Indian preamble is to articulate the guiding principles and aspirations that underline the constitution. It aims to secure justice, liberty, equality and fraternity for all citizens. The purpose is to establish a just and sovereign nation. The scope encompasses the entire constitution, serving as a key to interpret its provisions and uphold the democratic ideals enshrined within it.

Certainly, here are brief perspectives from some scholars and politicians on the Indian preamble :

Jawarlal Nehru (Politician) :

Nehru the first Prime Minister of India, played a key role in drafting the preamble. His vision emphasized democratic values, social justice, and equality.

Dr. B.R. Ambedkar (Scholar and Politician) :

As the Chief architect of the Indian constitution, Ambedkar stressed the significance of the preamble as a guide to the constitutional framework, highlighting the commitment to the justice, liberty, equality, and fraternity.

Granville Austin (American Historian) :

An American historian, Austin admired the Indian constitution and the preamble for its commitment to justice, liberty, equality and fraternity, seeing it as a transformative and visionary document.

Shyama Prasad Mukherjee (Politician) :

A prominent political figure, Mukherjee appreciated the preamble's reference to a sovereign, socialist, secular and democratic India, aligning with the principles he deemed essential for the nation's progress.

Arundhati Roy (Indian Author) :

Roy, an Indian author and activist, has critiqued the implementation of the preamble's ideals, often pointing out disparities in social and economic structures and raising questions about the practical realization of the stated principles.

Atal Bihari Vajpayee (Politician) :

The former Prime Minister emphasized the enduring values encapsulated in the preamble seeing it as a guide for the national moral compass and a testament to India's commitment to pluralism and democracy.

Arvind Datar (Legal Scholar) :

Arvind Datar, a contemporary legal scholar, has written extensively on constitutional law. His reviews often highlight the enduring relevance of the preamble in shaping the judicial interpretation of fundamental rights. Check his works from the late 20th century to the early 21st century.

These perspectives showcase a range of opinions, from those who see the preamble as a guiding light for a just and equal society to those who critique its implementations in practice.

Salient features of the Indian Constitution :

For understanding the Indian preamble, also discuss on some salient features of Indian constitution every constitution is unique in its way. The Indian constitution was developed in the mid twentieth century which in a way benefited the making of the constitution. By this time various countries across the world have developed their constitutions. This helped the makers to draw a vast amount of knowledge pertaining to various laws, rules, government systems, etc.

Analysing these constitutions and understanding what provisions could be taken from various constitutions and understanding what provisions could be taken from various constitutions helped in making our constitution much better. The influence of different laws from different parts of the world is quite pervasive. Our constitution in its unique way turned out to be an excellent document having distinctive features. Though we might have taken certain provisions from the constitutions of

other countries, our constitution has created a separate path, new patterns, and approaches of its own. Let's have a look at the salient features of constitution of India :-

- Lengthiest written constitution
- Elaborate preamble
- Socialist, welfare and secular state
- Parliamentary form of government
- Fundamental rights and duties
- Federal structures
- Independent judiciary
- A unique blend of rigidity and flexibility

Status of Preamble :

The preamble to the constitution aims to introduce the purpose behind the provisions of the constitution. The inspiration of the essence based on which the Indian constitution has been drafted is embodied in the preamble. It is the part highlighting the goals and principles of the constitutions. The preamble of the constitution of India embodies the ideology and the authority of the constitution.

The preamble paves the way for a better interpretation of the provisions of the constitution. Thus, it is a legitimate aid in interpreting the provisions of the constitution. In the constituent assembly debates, Sir Allads Krishnaswami opined that preamble is something that express 'What we thought for or dreamt for so long'. It has been assigned "the place of pride", by the makers of the Indian constitution. It breaks open the mind of the makers and helps them in realising the general purpose behind the enactment of various provisions of the constitution.

Berubari Case : It was used as a reference under Article 143(1) of the constitution which was on the implementation of the Indo-Pakistan Agreement related to the Berubari union and in exchanging the enclaves which were decided for consideration by the bench consisting of eight judges.

Through the Berubari case, the court stated that 'preamble is the key to open the mind of the makers' but it can not be considered as part of the constitution. Therefore, it is not enforceable in a court of law.

Kesavananda Bharti Case : In this case, for the first time, a bench of 13 judges was assembled to hear a writ petition. The court held that.

The preamble of the constitution will now be considered as a part of the constitution.

The preamble is not the supreme power or source of any restriction or prohibition but it plays an important role in the interpretation of status and provisions of the constitutions.

So, it can be concluded that preamble is part of the introductory part of the constitution.

In the 1995 case of Union Government VS LIC of India also, the Supreme Court has once again

held that preamble is the integral part of the constitution but it is not directly enforceable in a court of justice in India.

Amendment of the Preamble :

42nd Amendment Act, 1976 : After the judgement of the Kesvanand Bharti case, It was accepted that the preamble is a part of the constitution.

As a part of the constitution, preamble can be amended under Article 368 of the constitution, but the basic structure of the preamble can not be amended.

As of now, the preamble is only amended once through the 42nd Amendment Act, 1976.

The term 'Socialist', 'Secular' and integrity were added to the preamble through 42nd Amendment Act 1976.

Challenges and Relevance :

In the contemporary landscape, the preamble faces challenges that last its resilience. From socio-economic disparities to cultural diversity, the preamble's enduring relevance lies in its ability to adopt and guide the nation through complex socio-political scenarios.

Conclusion :

The Indian constitution preamble stands as a testament to the foresight of those who crafted it. Its eloquence and depth continue to inspire generations, shaping India's democratic journey. As the nation navigates the complexities of the 21st century, the preamble remains a compass, pointing towards the ideals that define the Indian identity.

References :

1. Definition of Indian constitution, <https://www.india.gov.in>cons...> Constitution of India-National Portal of India.
2. Definition of Indian Constitution, <https://unacademy.com>...> polity
3. Preamble-NCERT Book, Polity of Laxminath
4. Define the preamble, Drishti Ias 27 July, 2020
5. Preamble of the Indian constitution, Blog.ipleaders.in Sep. 18, 2023, 48082
6. Amendment of the Preamble, Drishti IAS, 27 July, 2020